

Supplementary Material: Information Bounds in Determining the 3D Orientation of a Single Emitter or Scatterer using Division-of-amplitude Polarimetry

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S1 Theory

S1.1 W Functions

The W functions in equation 3 are specified by¹

$$W_1^{0^\circ}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{4}\{2(A+B)(3+H) - [A+3AH+4B(1+H)+4C(1+H)\cos 2\phi] \sin^2 \theta + (1+3H)[B+C\cos 2\phi] \sin^4 \theta\} \quad (\text{S1})$$

$$W_{13}^{0^\circ}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{16}(1+3H)[B+C\cos 2\phi] \sin^2 2\theta \quad (\text{S2})$$

$$W_3^{0^\circ}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{4}[2-2H+(1+3H)\sin^2 \theta]\{A+[B+C\cos 2\phi] \sin^2 \theta\} \quad (\text{S3})$$

$$W_1^{90^\circ}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{4}\{2(A+B)(3+H) - [A+3AH+4B(1+H)-4C(1+H)\cos 2\phi] \sin^2 \theta + (1+3H)[B-C\cos 2\phi] \sin^4 \theta\} \quad (\text{S4})$$

$$W_{13}^{90^\circ}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{16}(1+3H)[B-C\cos 2\phi] \sin^2 2\theta \quad (\text{S5})$$

$$W_3^{90^\circ}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{4}[2-2H+(1+3H)\sin^2 \theta]\{A+[B-C\cos 2\phi] \sin^2 \theta\} \quad (\text{S6})$$

$$W_1^{45^\circ}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{4}\{2(A+B)(3+H) - [A+3AH+4B(1+H)+4C(1+H)\sin 2\phi]\sin^2\theta\} \\ + (1+3H)[B+C\sin 2\phi]\sin^4\theta \quad (\text{S7})$$

$$W_{13}^{45^\circ}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{16}(1+3H)[B+C\sin 2\phi]\sin^2 2\theta \quad (\text{S8})$$

$$W_3^{45^\circ}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{4}[2-2H+(1+3H)\sin^2\theta]\{A+[B+C\sin 2\phi]\sin^2\theta\} \quad (\text{S9})$$

$$W_1^{135^\circ}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{4}\{2(A+B)(3+H) - [A+3AH+4B(1+H)-4C(1+H)\sin 2\phi]\sin^2\theta\} \\ + (1+3H)[B-C\sin 2\phi]\sin^4\theta \quad (\text{S10})$$

$$W_{13}^{135^\circ}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{16}(1+3H)[B-C\sin 2\phi]\sin^2 2\theta \quad (\text{S11})$$

$$W_3^{135^\circ}(\lambda) = \frac{1}{4}[2-2H+(1+3H)\sin^2\theta]\{A+[B-C\sin 2\phi]\sin^2\theta\} \quad (\text{S12})$$

S1.2 Q and M terms, background case

The Q and M terms for the case of background in equations 9 to 12 are given by

$$Q_{\theta\theta 1\beta} = C^2 \cos^2(2\phi)(-2(16B(3+H)^2 + A(147+H(114+43H))) \\ + 4(1+3H)(4B(3+H)+A(11+H))\cos(2\theta) + A(1+3H)^2\cos(4\theta))\sin(2\theta)\alpha_1^2 \\ + 2A\sin(2\theta)\alpha_3(-1+3H)(4(-5+H)\cos(2\theta) + (1+3H)(3+\cos(4\theta)))\alpha_{13} \\ + 2(-5+H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta))^2\alpha_3 \\ + \alpha_1((1+3H)(5A(1+3H)\sin(2\theta)+4(4B(3+H)+A(11+H))\sin(4\theta)+A(1+3H)\sin(6\theta))\alpha_{13} \\ + 16(2(3+H)(2A(1+H)+B(3+H))\sin(2\theta)-(1+3H)(4A+B(3+H))\sin(4\theta))\alpha_3)^2 \\ \left(-1 + \frac{1}{\beta_0}\right)^2 I_0^\beta \quad (\text{S13})$$

$$M_{\theta\theta 1\beta} = \left(4096\text{NF}_s^4 \left(\frac{1}{16\text{NF}_s} (4(2(A+B)(3+H) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. - (A+3AH+4B(1+H)+4(1+H)C\cos(2\phi))\sin^2(\theta) \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + (1+3H)(B+C\cos(2\phi))\sin^4(\theta))\alpha_1 + (1+3H)(B+C\cos(2\phi))\sin^2(2\theta)\alpha_{13} \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + 4(2-2H+(1+3H)\sin^2(\theta))(A+(B+C\cos(2\phi))\sin^2(\theta))\alpha_3 \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_0}\right) + \frac{1}{\beta_0}\right) \quad (\text{S14})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\theta 2\beta} = & C^2 \sin^2(2\theta) \sin^2(2\phi) \left(- (16B(3+H)^2 + A(147+H(114+43H))) \right. \\
& + 4(1+3H)(4B(3+H) + A(11+H)) \cos(2\theta) + A(1+3H)^2 \cos(4\theta) \Big) \alpha_1^2 \\
& + A\alpha_3 \left(-(1+3H)(4(-5+H) \cos(2\theta) + (1+3H)(3+\cos(4\theta))) \alpha_{13} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 2(-5+H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta))^2 \alpha_3 \right) \\
& + \alpha_1 \left((1+3H)(4(4B(3+H) + A(11+H)) \cos(2\theta) + A(1+3H)(3+\cos(4\theta))) \alpha_{13} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 16((3+H)(2A(1+H) + B(3+H)) - (1+3H)(4A+B(3+H)) \cos(2\theta)) \alpha_3 \right)^2 \left(-1 \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}} \right)^2 I_{45}^\beta
\end{aligned} \tag{S15}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\theta 2\beta} = & \left(1024\text{NF}_s^4 \left(\frac{1}{16\text{NF}_s} (4(2(A+B)(3+H) + (1+3H) \sin^4(\theta)(B+C \sin(2\phi))) \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. - \sin^2(\theta)(A+3AH+4B(1+H) + 4(1+H)C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \alpha_1 \right. \\
& \quad \left. + (1+3H) \sin^2(2\theta)(B+C \sin(2\phi)) \alpha_{13} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 4(2-2H+(1+3H) \sin^2(\theta)) (A+\sin^2(\theta)(B+C \sin(2\phi))) \alpha_3 \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_{45}} \right) + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}} \right) \Big) \\
& \tag{S16}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\theta 3\beta} = & C^2 \cos^2(2\phi) \left(2(16B(3+H)^2 + A(147+H(114+43H))) \right. \tag{S17} \\
& + 4(1+3H)(4B(3+H) + A(11+H)) \cos(2\theta) + A(1+3H)^2 \cos(4\theta) \Big) \sin(2\theta) \alpha_1^2 \\
& + 2A \sin(2\theta) \alpha_3 \left((1+3H)(4(-5+H) \cos(2\theta) + (1+3H)(3+\cos(4\theta))) \alpha_{13} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - 2(-5+H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta))^2 \alpha_3 \right) \\
& + \alpha_1 \left(-2(1+3H)(4(4B(3+H) + A(11+H)) \cos(2\theta) + A(1+3H)(3+\cos(4\theta))) \sin(2\theta) \alpha_{13} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 16(-2(3+H)(2A(1+H) + B(3+H)) \sin(2\theta) + (1+3H)(4A+B(3+H)) \sin(4\theta)) \alpha_3 \right)^2 \left(-1 \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}} \right)^2 I_{90}^\beta
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\theta 3\beta} = & \left(4096\text{NF}_s^4 \left(\frac{1}{16\text{NF}_s} (4(2(A+B)(3+H) \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. - (A+3AH+4B(1+H) + 4(1+H)C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + (1+3H)(B-C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^4(\theta) \right) \alpha_1 + (1+3H)(B-C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(2\theta) \alpha_{13} \\
& \quad \left. + 4(2-2H+(1+3H) \sin^2(\theta)) (A+(B-C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta)) \alpha_3 \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_{90}} \right) + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}} \right) \Big) \\
& \tag{S18}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\theta 4\beta} &= \left(\frac{1}{\beta_{135}} \right. & (S19) \\
&\left. - 1 \right)^2 C^2 I_{135}^\beta \sin^2(2\theta) \sin^2(2\phi) (\alpha_1^2 ((3H+1)(4 \cos(2\theta)(A(H+11)+4B(H+3))+A(3H+1) \cos(4\theta)) \\
&\quad + A(H(43H+114)+147)+16B(H+3)^2) \\
&\quad + \alpha_1(\alpha_{13}(-3H-1)(4 \cos(2\theta)(A(H+11)+4B(H+3))+A(3H+1)(\cos(4\theta)+3)) \\
&\quad + 16\alpha_3((3H+1) \cos(2\theta)(4A+B(H+3))+(-H-3)(2A(H+1)+B(H+3)))) \\
&\quad + \alpha_3 A(\alpha_{13}(3H+1)(4(H-5) \cos(2\theta)+(3H+1)(\cos(4\theta)+3)) \\
&\quad - 2\alpha_3((3H+1) \cos(2\theta)+H-5)^2)^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\phi 1\beta} & & (S20) \\
&= C^2 \cos(2\phi) \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\phi) ((7+5H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta))\alpha_1 - 2(1+3H) \cos^2(\theta)\alpha_{13} \\
&\quad + (-5+H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta))\alpha_3) (-2(16B(3+H)^2+A(147+H(114+43H))) \\
&\quad + 4(1+3H)(4B(3+H)+A(11+H)) \cos(2\theta) + A(1+3H)^2 \cos(4\theta)) \sin(2\theta)\alpha_1^2 \\
&\quad + 2A \sin(2\theta)\alpha_3 ((-1-3H)(4(-5+H) \cos(2\theta)+(1+3H)(3+\cos(4\theta)))\alpha_{13} \\
&\quad + 2(-5+H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta))^2\alpha_3) \\
&\quad + \alpha_1 ((1+3H)(5A(1+3H) \sin(2\theta)+4(4B(3+H)+A(11+H)) \sin(4\theta)+A(1+3H) \sin(6\theta))\alpha_{13} \\
&\quad + 16(2(3+H)(2A(1+H)+B(3+H)) \sin(2\theta)-(1+3H)(4A+B(3+H)) \sin(4\theta))\alpha_3) \left(-1 \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{\beta_0} \right)^2 I_0^\beta
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\phi 1\beta} &= 16NF_s^2 \left((4(2(A+B)(3+H)-(A+3AH+4B(1+H)+4(1+H)C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) \right. \\
&\quad + (1+3H)(B+C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^4(\theta))\alpha_1 + (1+3H)(B+C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(2\theta)\alpha_{13} \\
&\quad \left. + 4(2-2H+(1+3H) \sin^2(\theta))(A+(B+C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta))\alpha_3 \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_0} \right) + \frac{16NF_s}{\beta_0} \right) \\
& & (S21)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\phi 2\beta} &= C^2 \cos(2\phi) \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\theta) \sin(2\phi) ((7+5H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta))\alpha_1 \\
&\quad - 2(1+3H) \cos^2(\theta)\alpha_{13} \\
&\quad + (-5+H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta))\alpha_3) ((-16B(3+H)^2-A(147+H(114+43H))) \\
&\quad - 4(1+3H)(4B(3+H)+A(11+H)) \cos(2\theta) - A(1+3H)^2 \cos(4\theta))\alpha_1^2 \\
&\quad + A\alpha_3 ((-1-3H)(4(-5+H) \cos(2\theta)+(1+3H)(3+\cos(4\theta)))\alpha_{13} \\
&\quad + 2(-5+H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta))^2\alpha_3) \\
&\quad + \alpha_1 ((1+3H)(4(4B(3+H)+A(11+H)) \cos(2\theta) + A(1+3H)(3+\cos(4\theta)))\alpha_{13} \\
&\quad + 16((3+H)(2A(1+H)+B(3+H)) - (1+3H)(4A+B(3+H)) \cos(2\theta))\alpha_3) \left(-1 \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}} \right)^2 I_{45}^\beta \\
& & (S22)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\phi 2\beta} = 8\text{NF}_s^2 & \left((4(2(A+B)(3+H) + (1+3H)\sin^4(\theta)(B+C\sin(2\phi))) \right. \\
& - \sin^2(\theta)(A+3AH+4B(1+H) + 4(1+H)C\sin(2\phi)))\alpha_1 \\
& + (1+3H)\sin^2(2\theta)(B+C\sin(2\phi))\alpha_{13} \\
& \left. + 4(2-2H+(1+3H)\sin^2(\theta))(A+\sin^2(\theta)(B+C\sin(2\phi)))\alpha_3 \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_{45}} \right) + \frac{16\text{NF}_s}{\beta_{45}} \Big) \\
& \tag{S23}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\phi 3\beta} = C^2 \cos(2\phi) \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\phi) & \left((7+5H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta))\alpha_1 - 2(1+3H)\cos^2(\theta)\alpha_{13} \right. \\
& + (-5+H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta))\alpha_3 \left(2(16B(3+H)^2 + A(147+H(114+43H))) \right. \\
& + 4(1+3H)(4B(3+H)+A(11+H))\cos(2\theta) + A(1+3H)^2\cos(4\theta) \Big) \sin(2\theta)\alpha_1^2 \\
& + 2A\sin(2\theta)\alpha_3 \left((1+3H)(4(-5+H)\cos(2\theta) + (1+3H)(3+\cos(4\theta)))\alpha_{13} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - 2(-5+H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta))^2\alpha_3 \right) \\
& + \alpha_1 (-2(1+3H)(4(4B(3+H)+A(11+H))\cos(2\theta) + A(1+3H)(3+\cos(4\theta)))\sin(2\theta)\alpha_{13} \\
& + 16(-2(3+H)(2A(1+H)+B(3+H))\sin(2\theta) + (1+3H)(4A+B(3+H))\sin(4\theta))\alpha_3) \Big) \left(-1 \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}} \right)^2 I_{90}^\beta \\
& \tag{S24}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\phi 3\beta} = 16\text{NF}_s^2 & \left((4(2(A+B)(3+H) - (A+3AH+4B(1+H) - 4(1+H)C\cos(2\phi))\sin^2(\theta)) \right. \\
& + (1+3H)(B-C\cos(2\phi))\sin^4(\theta))\alpha_1 + (1+3H)(B-C\cos(2\phi))\sin^2(2\theta)\alpha_{13} \\
& \left. + 4(2-2H+(1+3H)\sin^2(\theta))(A+(B-C\cos(2\phi))\sin^2(\theta))\alpha_3 \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_{90}} \right) + \frac{16\text{NF}_s}{\beta_{90}} \Big) \\
& \tag{S25}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\phi 4\beta} = C^2 \cos(2\phi) \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\theta) \sin(2\phi) & \left((7+5H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta))\alpha_1 \right. \\
& \quad \left. - 2(1+3H)\cos^2(\theta)\alpha_{13} \right. \\
& + (-5+H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta))\alpha_3 \left((16B(3+H)^2 + A(147+H(114+43H))) \right. \\
& \quad + (1+3H)(4(4B(3+H)+A(11+H))\cos(2\theta) + A(1+3H)\cos(4\theta)) \Big) \alpha_1^2 \\
& + A\alpha_3 \left((1+3H)(4(-5+H)\cos(2\theta) + (1+3H)(3+\cos(4\theta)))\alpha_{13} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - 2(-5+H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta))^2\alpha_3 \right) \\
& + \alpha_1 ((-1-3H)(4(4B(3+H)+A(11+H))\cos(2\theta) + A(1+3H)(3+\cos(4\theta)))\alpha_{13} \\
& + 16((-3-H)(2A(1+H)+B(3+H)) + (1+3H)(4A+B(3+H))\cos(2\theta))\alpha_3) \Big) \left(-1 \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \frac{1}{\beta_{135}} \right)^2 I_{135}^\beta \\
& \tag{S26}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\phi 4\beta} = 8\text{NF}_s^2 & \left((4(2(A+B)(3+H) + (1+3H)\sin^4(\theta)(B-C\sin(2\phi))) \right. \\
& - \sin^2(\theta)(A+3AH+4B(1+H) - 4(1+H)C\sin(2\phi)))\alpha_1 \\
& + (1+3H)\sin^2(2\theta)(B-C\sin(2\phi))\alpha_{13} \\
& \left. + 4(2-2H+(1+3H)\sin^2(\theta))(A+\sin^2(\theta)(B-C\sin(2\phi)))\alpha_3 \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_{135}} + \frac{16\text{NF}_s}{\beta_{135}} \right) \quad (\text{S27})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\phi\phi 1\beta} = C^2 \sin^4(\theta) \sin^2(2\phi) & \left((7+5H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta))\alpha_1 - 2(1+3H)\cos^2(\theta)\alpha_{13} \right. \\
& \left. + (-5+H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta))\alpha_3 \right)^2 \left(-1 + \frac{1}{\beta_0} \right)^2 I_0^\beta \quad (\text{S28})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\phi\phi 1\beta} = \text{NF}_s & \left((4(2(A+B)(3+H) - (A+3AH+4B(1+H) + 4(1+H)C\cos(2\phi))\sin^2(\theta)) \right. \\
& + (1+3H)(B+C\cos(2\phi))\sin^4(\theta))\alpha_1 + (1+3H)(B+C\cos(2\phi))\sin^2(2\theta)\alpha_{13} \\
& \left. + 4(2-2H+(1+3H)\sin^2(\theta))(A+(B+C\cos(2\phi))\sin^2(\theta))\alpha_3 \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_0} + \frac{16\text{NF}_s}{\beta_0} \right) \quad (\text{S29})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\phi\phi 2\beta} = C^2 \cos^2(2\phi) \sin^4(\theta) & \left((7+5H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta))\alpha_1 - 2(1+3H)\cos^2(\theta)\alpha_{13} \right. \\
& \left. + (-5+H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta))\alpha_3 \right)^2 \left(-1 + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}} \right)^2 I_{45}^\beta \quad (\text{S30})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\phi\phi 2\beta} = \text{NF}_s & \left((4(2(A+B)(3+H) + (1+3H)\sin^4(\theta)(B+C\sin(2\phi))) \right. \\
& - \sin^2(\theta)(A+3AH+4B(1+H) + 4(1+H)C\sin(2\phi)))\alpha_1 \\
& + (1+3H)\sin^2(2\theta)(B+C\sin(2\phi))\alpha_{13} \\
& \left. + 4(2-2H+(1+3H)\sin^2(\theta))(A+\sin^2(\theta)(B+C\sin(2\phi)))\alpha_3 \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_{45}} + \frac{16\text{NF}_s}{\beta_{45}} \right) \quad (\text{S31})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\phi\phi 3\beta} = C^2 \sin^4(\theta) \sin^2(2\phi) & \left((7+5H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta))\alpha_1 - 2(1+3H)\cos^2(\theta)\alpha_{13} \right. \\
& \left. + (-5+H+(1+3H)\cos(2\theta))\alpha_3 \right)^2 \left(-1 + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}} \right)^2 I_{90}^\beta \quad (\text{S32})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\phi\phi 3\beta} = \text{NF}_s \left((4(2(A+B)(3+H) - (A+3AH+4B(1+H) - 4(1+H)C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) \right. \\
+ (1+3H)(B-C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^4(\theta))\alpha_1 + (1+3H)(B-C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(2\theta)\alpha_{13} \\
\left. + 4(2-2H+(1+3H) \sin^2(\theta))(A+(B-C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta))\alpha_3 \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_{90}} \right) + \frac{16\text{NF}_s}{\beta_{90}} \Big) \quad (\text{S33})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\phi\phi 4\beta} = C^2 \cos^2(2\phi) \sin^4(\theta) \left((7+5H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta))\alpha_1 - 2(1+3H) \cos^2(\theta)\alpha_{13} \right. \\
\left. + (-5+H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta))\alpha_3 \right)^2 \left(-1 + \frac{1}{\beta_{135}} \right)^2 I_{135}^\beta \quad (\text{S34})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\phi\phi 4\beta} = \text{NF}_s \left((4(2(A+B)(3+H) + (1+3H) \sin^4(\theta)(B-C \sin(2\phi)) \right. \\
- \sin^2(\theta)(A+3AH+4B(1+H) - 4(1+H)C \sin(2\phi)))\alpha_1 \\
+ (1+3H) \sin^2(2\theta)(B-C \sin(2\phi))\alpha_{13} \\
\left. + 4(2-2H+(1+3H) \sin^2(\theta))(A+\sin^2(\theta)(B-C \sin(2\phi)))\alpha_3 \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_{135}} \right) + \frac{16\text{NF}_s}{\beta_{135}} \Big) \quad (\text{S35})
\end{aligned}$$

S1.3 Q and M terms, no background case

The Q and M terms for the case of no background in equations 9 to 12 are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\theta 1} = C^2 I_0 \cos^2(2\phi) \left(\alpha_1 (\alpha_{13} (3H+1) (4 \sin(4\theta) (A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) + 5A(3H+1) \sin(2\theta) \right. \\
+ A(3H+1) \sin(6\theta)) \\
+ 16\alpha_3 (2(H+3) \sin(2\theta) (2A(H+1) + B(H+3)) - (3H+1) \sin(4\theta) (4A+B(H+3))) \\
- 2\alpha_1^2 \sin(2\theta) (4(3H+1) \cos(2\theta) (A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) + A(3H+1)^2 \cos(4\theta) \\
+ A(H(43H+114) + 147) + 16B(H+3)^2) \\
+ 2\alpha_3 A \sin(2\theta) (2\alpha_3 ((3H+1) \cos(2\theta) + H-5)^2 \\
\left. + \alpha_{13} (-3H-1) (4(H-5) \cos(2\theta) + (3H+1) (\cos(4\theta) + 3))) \right)^2 \quad (\text{S36})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\theta 1} = 256\text{NF}_s^3 \left(4\alpha_1 \left(-\sin^2(\theta) (3AH+A+4B(H+1) + 4C(H+1) \cos(2\phi)) \right. \right. \\
+ 2(H+3)(A+B) + (3H+1) \sin^4(\theta) (B+C \cos(2\phi)) \Big) \\
+ 4\alpha_3 \left((3H+1) \sin^2(\theta) - 2H+2 \right) \left(A + \sin^2(\theta) (B+C \cos(2\phi)) \right) \\
\left. + \alpha_{13} (3H+1) \sin^2(2\theta) (B+C \cos(2\phi)) \right) \quad (\text{S37})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\theta 2} = & C^2 I_{45} \sin^2(2\theta) \sin^2(2\phi) \left(\alpha_1^2 \left(-4(3H+1) \cos(2\theta) (A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) \right. \right. \\
& - A(3H+1)^2 \cos(4\theta) - A(H(43H+114) + 147) - 16B(H+3)^2 \\
& + \alpha_1 (\alpha_{13}(3H+1)(4 \cos(2\theta)(A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) + A(3H+1)(\cos(4\theta) + 3)) \\
& + 16\alpha_3((H+3)(2A(H+1) + B(H+3)) - (3H+1) \cos(2\theta)(4A + B(H+3)))) \\
& + \alpha_3 A (2\alpha_3((3H+1) \cos(2\theta) + H - 5)^2 \\
& \left. \left. + \alpha_{13}(-3H-1)(4(H-5) \cos(2\theta) + (3H+1)(\cos(4\theta) + 3))) \right)^2 \right) \quad (S38)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\theta 2} = & 64NF_s^3 \left(4\alpha_1 \left(-\sin^2(\theta)(3AH + A + 4B(H+1) + 4C(H+1) \sin(2\phi)) \right. \right. \\
& + 2(H+3)(A+B) + (3H+1) \sin^4(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) \left. \right) \quad (S39) \\
& + 4\alpha_3 \left((3H+1) \sin^2(\theta) - 2H + 2 \right) \left(A + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \\
& + \alpha_{13}(3H+1) \sin^2(2\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\theta 3} = & C^2 I_{90} \cos^2(2\phi) \left(2\alpha_1^2 \sin(2\theta) \left(4(3H+1) \cos(2\theta)(A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) \right. \right. \\
& + A(3H+1)^2 \cos(4\theta) + A(H(43H+114) + 147) + 16B(H+3)^2 \\
& + \alpha_1 (16\alpha_3((3H+1) \sin(4\theta)(4A+B(H+3)) - 2(H+3) \sin(2\theta)(2A(H+1) + B(H+3))) \\
& - 2\alpha_{13}(3H+1) \sin(2\theta)(4 \cos(2\theta)(A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) + A(3H+1)(\cos(4\theta) + 3))) \\
& + 2\alpha_3 A \sin(2\theta) \left(\alpha_{13}(3H+1)(4(H-5) \cos(2\theta) + (3H+1)(\cos(4\theta) + 3)) \right. \\
& \left. \left. - 2\alpha_3((3H+1) \cos(2\theta) + H - 5)^2 \right) \right)^2 \quad (S40)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\theta 3} = & 256NF_s^3 \left(4\alpha_1 \left(-\sin^2(\theta)(3AH + A + 4B(H+1) - 4C(H+1) \cos(2\phi)) \right. \right. \\
& + 2(H+3)(A+B) + (3H+1) \sin^4(\theta)(B - C \cos(2\phi)) \left. \right) \quad (S41) \\
& + 4\alpha_3 \left((3H+1) \sin^2(\theta) - 2H + 2 \right) \left(A + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \cos(2\phi)) \right) \\
& + \alpha_{13}(3H+1) \sin^2(2\theta)(B - C \cos(2\phi))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\theta 4} & \quad (S42) \\
= & C^2 I_{135} \sin^2(2\theta) \sin^2(2\phi) \left(\alpha_1^2 \left((3H+1)(4 \cos(2\theta)(A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) + A(3H+1) \cos(4\theta)) \right. \right. \\
& + A(H(43H+114) + 147) + 16B(H+3)^2 \\
& + \alpha_1 (\alpha_{13}(-3H-1)(4 \cos(2\theta)(A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) + A(3H+1)(\cos(4\theta) + 3)) \\
& + 16\alpha_3((3H+1) \cos(2\theta)(4A + B(H+3)) + (-H-3)(2A(H+1) + B(H+3)))) \\
& + \alpha_3 A \left(\alpha_{13}(3H+1)(4(H-5) \cos(2\theta) + (3H+1)(\cos(4\theta) + 3)) \right. \\
& \left. \left. - 2\alpha_3((3H+1) \cos(2\theta) + H - 5)^2 \right) \right)^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\theta 4} = & 64NF_s^3 \left(4\alpha_1 \left(-\sin^2(\theta)(3AH + A + 4B(H+1) - 4C(H+1) \sin(2\phi)) \right. \right. \\
& + 2(H+3)(A+B) + (3H+1) \sin^4(\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi)) \left. \right) \quad (S43) \\
& + 4\alpha_3 \left((3H+1) \sin^2(\theta) - 2H + 2 \right) \left(A + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \\
& + \alpha_{13}(3H+1) \sin^2(2\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi))
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\phi 1} = C^2 I_0 \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\phi) \cos(2\phi) & \left(-2\alpha_{13}(3H+1) \cos^2(\theta) \right. \\
& + \alpha_1((3H+1) \cos(2\theta) + 5H+7) + \alpha_3((3H+1) \cos(2\theta) + H \\
& - 5) \left(\alpha_1(\alpha_{13}(3H+1)(4 \sin(4\theta)(A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) + 5A(3H+1) \sin(2\theta) + A(3H+1) \sin(6\theta)) \right. \\
& + 16\alpha_3(2(H+3) \sin(2\theta)(2A(H+1) + B(H+3)) - (3H+1) \sin(4\theta)(4A+B(H+3))) \\
& - 2\alpha_1^2 \sin(2\theta) (4(3H+1) \cos(2\theta)(A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) + A(3H+1)^2 \cos(4\theta) \\
& + A(H(43H+114) + 147) + 16B(H+3)^2) \\
& + 2\alpha_3 A \sin(2\theta) (2\alpha_3((3H+1) \cos(2\theta) + H-5)^2 \\
& \left. + \alpha_{13}(-3H-1)(4(H-5) \cos(2\theta) + (3H+1)(\cos(4\theta) + 3))) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S44}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\phi 1} = 16NF_s^2 & \left(4\alpha_1 (-\sin^2(\theta)(3AH + A + 4B(H+1) + 4C(H+1) \cos(2\phi)) \right. \\
& + 2(H+3)(A+B) + (3H+1) \sin^4(\theta)(B+C \cos(2\phi))) \\
& + 4\alpha_3 ((3H+1) \sin^2(\theta) - 2H+2) (A + \sin^2(\theta)(B+C \cos(2\phi))) \\
& \left. + \alpha_{13}(3H+1) \sin^2(2\theta)(B+C \cos(2\phi)) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S45}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\phi 2} = C^2 I_{45} \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\theta) \sin(2\phi) \cos(2\phi) & \left(-2\alpha_{13}(3H+1) \cos^2(\theta) \right. \\
& + \alpha_1((3H+1) \cos(2\theta) + 5H+7) \\
& + \alpha_3((3H+1) \cos(2\theta) + H-5) \left(\alpha_1^2 (-4(3H+1) \cos(2\theta)(A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) \right. \\
& - A(3H+1)^2 \cos(4\theta) - A(H(43H+114) + 147) - 16B(H+3)^2) \\
& + \alpha_1(\alpha_{13}(3H+1)(4 \cos(2\theta)(A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) + A(3H+1)(\cos(4\theta) + 3)) \\
& + 16\alpha_3((H+3)(2A(H+1) + B(H+3)) - (3H+1) \cos(2\theta)(4A+B(H+3)))) \\
& + \alpha_3 A (2\alpha_3((3H+1) \cos(2\theta) + H-5)^2 \\
& \left. + \alpha_{13}(-3H-1)(4(H-5) \cos(2\theta) + (3H+1)(\cos(4\theta) + 3))) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S46}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\phi 2} = 8NF_s^2 & \left(4\alpha_1 (-\sin^2(\theta)(3AH + A + 4B(H+1) + 4C(H+1) \sin(2\phi)) \right. \\
& + 2(H+3)(A+B) + (3H+1) \sin^4(\theta)(B+C \sin(2\phi))) \\
& + 4\alpha_3 ((3H+1) \sin^2(\theta) - 2H+2) (A + \sin^2(\theta)(B+C \sin(2\phi))) \\
& \left. + \alpha_{13}(3H+1) \sin^2(2\theta)(B+C \sin(2\phi)) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S47}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\phi 3} = C^2 I_{90} \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\phi) \cos(2\phi) & \left(-2\alpha_{13}(3H+1) \cos^2(\theta) + \alpha_1((3H+1) \cos(2\theta) + 5H+7) \right. \\
& + \alpha_3((3H+1) \cos(2\theta) + H \\
& - 5) \left(2\alpha_1^2 \sin(2\theta) (4(3H+1) \cos(2\theta)(A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) \right. \\
& + A(3H+1)^2 \cos(4\theta) + A(H(43H+114) + 147) + 16B(H+3)^2) \\
& + \alpha_1(16\alpha_3((3H+1) \sin(4\theta)(4A+B(H+3)) - 2(H+3) \sin(2\theta)(2A(H+1) + B(H+3))) \\
& - 2\alpha_{13}(3H+1) \sin(2\theta)(4 \cos(2\theta)(A(H+11) + 4B(H+3)) + A(3H+1)(\cos(4\theta) + 3))) \\
& + 2\alpha_3 A \sin(2\theta) (\alpha_{13}(3H+1)(4(H-5) \cos(2\theta) + (3H+1)(\cos(4\theta) + 3)) \\
& \left. - 2\alpha_3((3H+1) \cos(2\theta) + H-5)^2) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S48}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\phi 3} = & 16Nf_s^2 \left(4\alpha_1 \left(-\sin^2(\theta)(3AH + A + 4B(H + 1) - 4C(H + 1)\cos(2\phi)) \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. + 2(H + 3)(A + B) + (3H + 1)\sin^4(\theta)(B - C\cos(2\phi)) \right) \right. \\
& \left. + 4\alpha_3 \left((3H + 1)\sin^2(\theta) - 2H + 2 \right) \left(A + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C\cos(2\phi)) \right) \right. \\
& \left. + \alpha_{13}(3H + 1)\sin^2(2\theta)(B - C\cos(2\phi)) \right) \quad (S49)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\theta\phi 4} = & C^2 I_{135} \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\theta) \sin(2\phi) \cos(2\phi) \left(-2\alpha_{13}(3H + 1)\cos^2(\theta) \right. \\
& \left. + \alpha_1((3H + 1)\cos(2\theta) + 5H + 7) + \alpha_3((3H + 1)\cos(2\theta) + H \right. \\
& \left. - 5) \right) \left(\alpha_1^2 \left((3H + 1)(4\cos(2\theta)(A(H + 11) + 4B(H + 3)) + A(3H + 1)\cos(4\theta)) \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. + A(H(43H + 114) + 147) + 16B(H + 3)^2 \right) \right. \\
& \left. + \alpha_1 \left(\alpha_{13}(-3H - 1)(4\cos(2\theta)(A(H + 11) + 4B(H + 3)) + A(3H + 1)(\cos(4\theta) + 3)) \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. + 16\alpha_3((3H + 1)\cos(2\theta)(4A + B(H + 3)) + (-H - 3)(2A(H + 1) + B(H + 3))) \right) \right. \\
& \left. + \alpha_3 A \left(\alpha_{13}(3H + 1)(4(H - 5)\cos(2\theta) + (3H + 1)(\cos(4\theta) + 3)) \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. - 2\alpha_3((3H + 1)\cos(2\theta) + H - 5)^2 \right) \right) \quad (S50)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\theta\phi 4} = & 8NF_s^2 \left(4\alpha_1 \left(-\sin^2(\theta)(3AH + A + 4B(H + 1) - 4C(H + 1)\sin(2\phi)) \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. + 2(H + 3)(A + B) + (3H + 1)\sin^4(\theta)(B - C\sin(2\phi)) \right) \right. \\
& \left. + 4\alpha_3 \left((3H + 1)\sin^2(\theta) - 2H + 2 \right) \left(A + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C\sin(2\phi)) \right) \right. \\
& \left. + \alpha_{13}(3H + 1)\sin^2(2\theta)(B - C\sin(2\phi)) \right) \quad (S51)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\phi\phi 1} = & C^2 I_0 \sin^4(\theta) \sin^2(2\phi) \left(-2\alpha_{13}(3H + 1)\cos^2(\theta) + \alpha_1((3H + 1)\cos(2\theta) + 5H + 7) \right. \\
& \left. + \alpha_3((3H + 1)\cos(2\theta) + H - 5) \right)^2 \quad (S52)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\phi\phi 1} = & NF_s \left(4\alpha_1 \left(-\sin^2(\theta)(3AH + A + 4B(H + 1) + 4C(H + 1)\cos(2\phi)) \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. + 2(H + 3)(A + B) + (3H + 1)\sin^4(\theta)(B + C\cos(2\phi)) \right) \right. \\
& \left. + 4\alpha_3 \left((3H + 1)\sin^2(\theta) - 2H + 2 \right) \left(A + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C\cos(2\phi)) \right) \right. \\
& \left. + \alpha_{13}(3H + 1)\sin^2(2\theta)(B + C\cos(2\phi)) \right) \quad (S53)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\phi\phi 2} = & C^2 I_{45} \sin^4(\theta) \cos^2(2\phi) \left(-2\alpha_{13}(3H + 1)\cos^2(\theta) \right. \\
& \left. + \alpha_1((3H + 1)\cos(2\theta) + 5H + 7) + \alpha_3((3H + 1)\cos(2\theta) + H - 5) \right)^2 \quad (S54)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\phi\phi 2} = \text{NF}_s & \left(4\alpha_1 \left(-\sin^2(\theta)(3AH + A + 4B(H + 1) + 4C(H + 1) \sin(2\phi)) \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 2(H + 3)(A + B) + (3H + 1) \sin^4(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 4\alpha_3 \left((3H + 1) \sin^2(\theta) - 2H + 2 \right) \left(A + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \alpha_{13}(3H + 1) \sin^2(2\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \quad (\text{S55})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\phi\phi 3} = C^2 I_{90} \sin^4(\theta) \sin^2(2\phi) & \left(-2\alpha_{13}(3H + 1) \cos^2(\theta) \right. \\
& \left. + \alpha_1((3H + 1) \cos(2\theta) + 5H + 7) + \alpha_3((3H + 1) \cos(2\theta) + H - 5) \right)^2 \quad (\text{S56})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\phi\phi 3} = \text{NF}_s & \left(4\alpha_1 \left(-\sin^2(\theta)(3AH + A + 4B(H + 1) - 4C(H + 1) \cos(2\phi)) \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 2(H + 3)(A + B) + (3H + 1) \sin^4(\theta)(B - C \cos(2\phi)) \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 4\alpha_3 \left((3H + 1) \sin^2(\theta) - 2H + 2 \right) \left(A + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \cos(2\phi)) \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \alpha_{13}(3H + 1) \sin^2(2\theta)(B - C \cos(2\phi)) \right) \quad (\text{S57})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_{\phi\phi 4} = C^2 I_{135} \sin^4(\theta) \cos^2(2\phi) & \left(-2\alpha_{13}(3H + 1) \cos^2(\theta) \right. \\
& \left. + \alpha_1((3H + 1) \cos(2\theta) + 5H + 7) + \alpha_3((3H + 1) \cos(2\theta) + H - 5) \right)^2 \quad (\text{S58})
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{\phi\phi 4} = \text{NF}_s & \left(4\alpha_1 \left(-\sin^2(\theta)(3AH + A + 4B(H + 1) - 4C(H + 1) \sin(2\phi)) \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + 2(H + 3)(A + B) + (3H + 1) \sin^4(\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 4\alpha_3 \left((3H + 1) \sin^2(\theta) - 2H + 2 \right) \left(A + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \alpha_{13}(3H + 1) \sin^2(2\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \quad (\text{S59})
\end{aligned}$$

S1.4 Fisher Information for Fluorescence Case

The Fisher information matrix elements for the case of fluorescence with background are:

$$\begin{aligned}
J_{\theta\theta,f,\beta} = T & \left(\frac{A^2 (\beta_{45} - 1)^2 C^2 I_{45}^\beta \sin^2(2\theta) \sin^2(2\phi)}{4\beta_{45} (A + B \sin^2(\theta))^3 (\beta_{45} (A + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi))) + 3A + \sin^2(\theta)(3B - C \sin(2\phi)))} \right. \\
& + \frac{A^2 (\beta_{90} - 1)^2 C^2 I_{90}^\beta \sin^2(\theta) \cos^2(\theta) \cos^2(2\phi)}{\beta_{90} (A + B \sin^2(\theta))^3 (\beta_{90} (A + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \cos(2\phi))) + 3A + \sin^2(\theta)(3B + C \cos(2\phi)))} + \\
& \frac{A^2 (\beta_{135} - 1)^2 C^2 I_{135}^\beta \sin^2(2\theta) \sin^2(2\phi)}{4\beta_{135} (A + B \sin^2(\theta))^3 (\beta_{135} (A + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi))) + 3A + \sin^2(\theta)(3B + C \sin(2\phi)))} + \\
& \left. \frac{A^2 (\beta_0 - 1)^2 C^2 I_0^\beta \sin^2(\theta) \cos^2(\theta) \cos^2(2\phi)}{\beta_0 (A + B \sin^2(\theta))^3 \left(\frac{1}{2} (\beta_0 + 3) (2A - B \cos(2\theta) + B) + (\beta_0 - 1) C \sin^2(\theta) \cos(2\phi) \right)} \right) \quad (S60)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
J_{\theta\phi,f,\beta} = T & \left(\frac{A (\beta_{45} - 1)^2 C^2 I_{45}^\beta \cot(\theta) \csc^2(\theta) \sin(4\phi)}{2\beta_{45} (A \csc^2(\theta) + B)^2 (\beta_{45} (A \csc^2(\theta) + B + C \sin(2\phi)) + 3A \csc^2(\theta) + 3B - C \sin(2\phi))} \right. \\
& - \frac{A (\beta_{90} - 1)^2 C^2 I_{90}^\beta \cot(\theta) \csc^2(\theta) \sin(4\phi)}{2\beta_{90} (A \csc^2(\theta) + B)^2 (\beta_{90} (A \csc^2(\theta) + B - C \cos(2\phi)) + 3(A \csc^2(\theta) + B) + C \cos(2\phi))} \\
& + \frac{A (\beta_{135} - 1)^2 C^2 I_{135}^\beta \cot(\theta) \csc^2(\theta) \sin(4\phi)}{2\beta_{135} (A \csc^2(\theta) + B)^2 (\beta_{135} (A \csc^2(\theta) + B - C \sin(2\phi)) + 3A \csc^2(\theta) + 3B + C \sin(2\phi))} \\
& \left. - \frac{A (\beta_0 - 1)^2 C^2 I_0^\beta \cot(\theta) \csc^2(\theta) \sin(4\phi)}{2\beta_0 (A \csc^2(\theta) + B)^2 (\beta_0 (A \csc^2(\theta) + B + C \cos(2\phi)) + 3(A \csc^2(\theta) + B) - C \cos(2\phi))} \right) \quad (S61)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
J_{\phi\phi,f,\beta} = T & \left(\frac{(\beta_{45} - 1)^2 C^2 I_{45}^\beta \cos^2(2\phi)}{\beta_{45} (A \csc^2(\theta) + B) (\beta_{45} (A \csc^2(\theta) + B + C \sin(2\phi)) + 3A \csc^2(\theta) + 3B - C \sin(2\phi))} \right. \\
& + \frac{(\beta_{90} - 1)^2 C^2 I_{90}^\beta \sin^2(2\phi)}{\beta_{90} (A \csc^2(\theta) + B) (\beta_{90} (A \csc^2(\theta) + B - C \cos(2\phi)) + 3(A \csc^2(\theta) + B) + C \cos(2\phi))} + \\
& \frac{(\beta_{135} - 1)^2 C^2 I_{135}^\beta \cos^2(2\phi)}{\beta_{135} (A \csc^2(\theta) + B) (\beta_{135} (A \csc^2(\theta) + B - C \sin(2\phi)) + 3A \csc^2(\theta) + 3B + C \sin(2\phi))} + \\
& \left. \frac{(\beta_0 - 1)^2 C^2 I_0^\beta \sin^2(2\phi)}{\beta_0 (A \csc^2(\theta) + B) (\beta_0 (A \csc^2(\theta) + B + C \cos(2\phi)) + 3(A \csc^2(\theta) + B) - C \cos(2\phi))} \right) \quad (S62)
\end{aligned}$$

in the case of background. In the case of no background, these reduce to:

$$\begin{aligned}
J_{\theta\theta,f} = T \frac{1}{4(A + B \sin^2(\theta))^3} A^2 C^2 & \\
& \left(4 \cos^2(\theta) \cos^2(2\phi) \left(\frac{I_0^0}{B + C \cos(2\phi) + A \csc^2(\theta)} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + \frac{I_{90}^0}{B - C \cos(2\phi) + A \csc^2(\theta)} \right) \right. \\
& + \sin^2(2\theta) \sin^2(2\phi) \left(\frac{I_{45}^0}{A + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi))} + \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \frac{I_{135}^0}{A + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi))} \right) \right) \quad (S63)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
J_{\theta\phi,f} = T \frac{1}{2(B + A \csc^2(\theta))^2} AC^2 & \\
& \cot(\theta) \csc^2(\theta) \sin(4\phi) \left(- \frac{I_0^0}{B + C \cos(2\phi) + A \csc^2(\theta)} \right. \\
& \quad + \frac{I_{45}^0}{B + A \csc^2(\theta) + C \sin(2\phi)} \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{I_{90}^0}{B - C \cos(2\phi) + A \csc^2(\theta)} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \frac{I_{135}^0}{B + A \csc^2(\theta) - C \sin(2\phi)} \right) \quad (S64)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
J_{\phi\phi,f} = T \frac{1}{B + A \csc^2(\theta)} C^2 & \\
& \left(\sin^2(2\phi) \left(\frac{I_0^0}{B + C \cos(2\phi) + A \csc^2(\theta)} + \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. \frac{I_{90}^0}{B - C \cos(2\phi) + A \csc^2(\theta)} \right) \right. \\
& + \cos^2(2\phi) \left(\frac{I_{45}^0}{B + A \csc^2(\theta) + C \sin(2\phi)} \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + \frac{I_{135}^0}{B + A \csc^2(\theta) - C \sin(2\phi)} \right) \right). \quad (S65)
\end{aligned}$$

S1.5 MLE for Scattering Experiment

We may derive the MLE for θ for the scattering experiment (where the number of photons in the 0, 45, 90 and 135° channels are n_0 , n_{45} , n_{90} and n_{135} respectively) using the multinomial approach (equation 14 of Watkins and Yang),² and where $n_{tot} = n_0 + n_{45} + n_{90} + n_{135}$ as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{4} \left(-(A + 3AH + B(3 + H) + (3 + H)C \cos(2\phi)) \sin(2\theta) (\alpha_1 - \alpha_3) \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{1}{2} (1 + 3H)(B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin(4\theta) (\alpha_1 - \alpha_{13} + \alpha_3) \right) \left(\frac{16n_0}{R_{\theta 1}} - \frac{n_{tot}}{R_{\theta 2}} \right) \\
& \quad + \frac{1}{8} (2 \sin(2\theta)(-B(3 + H) - A(1 + 3H)) \\
& \quad - (3 + H)C \sin(2\phi) - (1 + 3H) \cos(2\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi))) \alpha_1 \\
& \quad + (1 + 3H) \sin(4\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) \alpha_{13} \\
& \quad + 2 \sin(2\theta)(A + 3AH + B(3 + H) + (3 + H)C \sin(2\phi) \\
& \quad - (1 + 3H) \cos(2\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi))) \alpha_3 \left(\frac{16n_{45}}{R_{\theta 3}} - \frac{n_{tot}}{R_{\theta 2}} \right) \\
& \quad + \frac{1}{4} \left(-(A + 3AH + B(3 + H) - (3 + H)C \cos(2\phi)) \sin(2\theta) (\alpha_1 - \alpha_3) \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{1}{2} (1 + 3H)(B - C \cos(2\phi)) \sin(4\theta) (\alpha_1 - \alpha_{13} + \alpha_3) \right) \left(\frac{16n_{90}}{R_{\theta 4}} - \frac{n_{tot}}{R_{\theta 2}} \right) \\
& \quad + \frac{1}{8} (2 \sin(2\theta)(-B(3 + H) - A(1 + 3H)) \\
& \quad + (3 + H)C \sin(2\phi) - (1 + 3H) \cos(2\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi))) \alpha_1 \\
& \quad + (1 + 3H) \sin(4\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi)) \alpha_{13} \\
& \quad + 2 \sin(2\theta)(A + 3AH + B(3 + H) - (3 + H)C \sin(2\phi) \\
& \quad - (1 + 3H) \cos(2\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi))) \alpha_3 \left(\frac{16n_{135}}{R_{\theta 5}} - \frac{n_{tot}}{R_{\theta 2}} \right) = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{S66}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{\theta 1} = & 4 \left(2(A + B)(3 + H) - (A + 3AH + 4B(1 + H) + 4(1 + H)C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + (1 + 3H)(B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^4(\theta) \right) \alpha_1 + (1 + 3H)(B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(2\theta) \alpha_{13} \\
& \quad + 4 \left(2 - 2H + (1 + 3H) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \left(A + (B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \alpha_3 + \frac{16}{-1 + \beta_0}
\end{aligned} \tag{S67}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{\theta 2} = & \left(2(A + B)(3 + H) - (A + 3AH + 4B(1 + H)) \sin^2(\theta) + B(1 + 3H) \sin^4(\theta) \right) \alpha_1 \\
& \quad + B(1 + 3H) \cos^2(\theta) \sin^2(\theta) \alpha_{13} + \left(A + B \sin^2(\theta) \right) \left(2 - 2H + (1 + 3H) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \alpha_3 \\
& \quad + \frac{1}{-1 + \beta_0} + \frac{1}{-1 + \beta_{45}} + \frac{1}{-1 + \beta_{90}} + \frac{1}{-1 + \beta_{135}}
\end{aligned} \tag{S68}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{\theta_3} = & 4 \left(2(A+B)(3+H) + (1+3H) \sin^4(\theta)(B+C \sin(2\phi)) \right. \\
& \left. - \sin^2(\theta)(A+3AH+4B(1+H)+4(1+H)C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \alpha_1 \\
& + (1+3H) \sin^2(2\theta)(B+C \sin(2\phi)) \alpha_{13} \\
& + 4 \left(2-2H+(1+3H) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \left(A+\sin^2(\theta)(B+C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \alpha_3 + \frac{16}{-1+\beta_{45}}
\end{aligned} \tag{S69}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{\theta_4} = & 4 \left(2(A+B)(3+H) - (A+3AH+4B(1+H)-4(1+H)C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) \right. \\
& \left. + (1+3H)(B-C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^4(\theta) \right) \alpha_1 + (1+3H)(B-C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(2\theta) \alpha_{13} \\
& + 4 \left(2-2H+(1+3H) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \left(A+(B-C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \alpha_3 + \frac{16}{-1+\beta_{90}}
\end{aligned} \tag{S70}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{\theta_5} = & 4 \left(2(A+B)(3+H) + (1+3H) \sin^4(\theta)(B-C \sin(2\phi)) \right. \\
& \left. - \sin^2(\theta)(A+3AH+4B(1+H)-4(1+H)C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \alpha_1 \\
& + (1+3H) \sin^2(2\theta)(B-C \sin(2\phi)) \alpha_{13} \\
& + 4 \left(2-2H+(1+3H) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \left(A+\sin^2(\theta)(B-C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \alpha_3 + \frac{16}{-1+\beta_{135}}
\end{aligned} \tag{S71}$$

and the MLE for ϕ as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{4} C \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\phi) \left((7+5H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta)) \alpha_1 - 2(1+3H) \cos^2(\theta) \alpha_{13} \right. \\
& \left. + (-5+H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta)) \alpha_3 \right) \left(\frac{16n_0}{R_{\phi_1}} - \frac{n_{\text{tot}}}{R_{\phi_2}} \right) \\
& - \frac{1}{4} C \cos(2\phi) \sin^2(\theta) \left((7+5H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta)) \alpha_1 \right. \\
& \left. - 2(1+3H) \cos^2(\theta) \alpha_{13} + (-5+H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta)) \alpha_3 \right) \left(\frac{16n_{45}}{R_{\phi_3}} - \frac{n_{\text{tot}}}{R_{\phi_2}} \right) \\
& - \frac{1}{4} C \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\phi) \left((7+5H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta)) \alpha_1 \right. \\
& \left. - 2(1+3H) \cos^2(\theta) \alpha_{13} + (-5+H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta)) \alpha_3 \right) \left(\frac{16n_{90}}{R_{\phi_4}} - \frac{n_{\text{tot}}}{R_{\phi_2}} \right) \\
& + \frac{1}{4} C \cos(2\phi) \sin^2(\theta) \left((7+5H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta)) \alpha_1 - 2(1+3H) \cos^2(\theta) \alpha_{13} \right. \\
& \left. + (-5+H+(1+3H) \cos(2\theta)) \alpha_3 \right) \left(\frac{16n_{135}}{R_{\phi_5}} - \frac{n_{\text{tot}}}{R_{\phi_2}} \right) = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{S72}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{\phi 1} = & 4 \left(2(A + B)(3 + H) - (A + 3AH + 4B(1 + H) + 4(1 + H)C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) \right. \\
& + (1 + 3H)(B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^4(\theta) \left. \right) \alpha_1 + (1 + 3H)(B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(2\theta) \alpha_{13} \\
& + 4 \left(2 - 2H + (1 + 3H) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \left(A + (B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \alpha_3 + \frac{16}{-1 + \beta_0}
\end{aligned} \tag{S73}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{\phi 2} = & \left(2(A + B)(3 + H) - (A + 3AH + 4B(1 + H)) \sin^2(\theta) + B(1 + 3H) \sin^4(\theta) \right) \alpha_1 \\
& + B(1 + 3H) \cos^2(\theta) \sin^2(\theta) \alpha_{13} + \left(A + B \sin^2(\theta) \right) \left(2 - 2H + (1 + 3H) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \alpha_3 \\
& + \frac{1}{-1 + \beta_0} + \frac{1}{-1 + \beta_{45}} + \frac{1}{-1 + \beta_{90}} + \frac{1}{-1 + \beta_{135}}
\end{aligned} \tag{S74}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{\phi 3} = & 4 \left(2(A + B)(3 + H) + (1 + 3H) \sin^4(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) \right. \\
& \left. - \sin^2(\theta)(A + 3AH + 4B(1 + H) + 4(1 + H)C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \alpha_1 \\
& + (1 + 3H) \sin^2(2\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) \alpha_{13} \\
& + 4 \left(2 - 2H + (1 + 3H) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \left(A + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \alpha_3 + \frac{16}{-1 + \beta_{45}}
\end{aligned} \tag{S75}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{\phi 4} = & 4 \left(2(A + B)(3 + H) - (A + 3AH + 4B(1 + H) - 4(1 + H)C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) \right. \\
& + (1 + 3H)(B - C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^4(\theta) \left. \right) \alpha_1 + (1 + 3H)(B - C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(2\theta) \alpha_{13} \\
& + 4 \left(2 - 2H + (1 + 3H) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \left(A + (B - C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \alpha_3 + \frac{16}{-1 + \beta_{90}}
\end{aligned} \tag{S76}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
R_{\phi 5} = & 4 \left(2(A + B)(3 + H) + (1 + 3H) \sin^4(\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi)) \right. \\
& \left. - \sin^2(\theta)(A + 3AH + 4B(1 + H) - 4(1 + H)C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \alpha_1 \\
& + (1 + 3H) \sin^2(2\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi)) \alpha_{13} \\
& + 4 \left(2 - 2H + (1 + 3H) \sin^2(\theta) \right) \left(A + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi)) \right) \alpha_3 + \frac{16}{-1 + \beta_{135}}
\end{aligned} \tag{S77}$$

both of which may be numerically solved to give θ and ϕ . Note that if multiple wavelengths of light are used it is far faster to use average α_i values.

S1.6 MLE for Fluorescence Experiment

We may also derive the MLE for θ for the fluorescence experiment (where the number of photons in the 0, 45, 90 and 135° channels are n_0 , n_{45} , n_{90} and n_{135} respectively) using the multinomial approach (equation 14 of Watkins and Yang)² as

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sin(2\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) \left(\frac{n_{45}}{A + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}-1} + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi))} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{n_{\text{tot}}}{4A + \frac{1}{\beta_0-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{135}-1} + 4B \sin^2(\theta)} \right) \\
& + \sin(2\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi)) \left(\frac{n_{135}}{A + \frac{1}{\beta_{135}-1} + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi))} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{n_{\text{tot}}}{4A + \frac{1}{\beta_0-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{135}-1} + 4B \sin^2(\theta)} \right) \\
& + \sin(2\theta)(B + C \cos(2\phi)) \left(\frac{n_0}{A + \frac{1}{\beta_0-1} + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \cos(2\phi))} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{n_{\text{tot}}}{4A + \frac{1}{\beta_0-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{135}-1} + 4B \sin^2(\theta)} \right) \\
& + \sin(2\theta)(B - C \cos(2\phi)) \left(\frac{n_{90}}{A + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}-1} + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \cos(2\phi))} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{n_{\text{tot}}}{4A + \frac{1}{\beta_0-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{135}-1} + 4B \sin^2(\theta)} \right) = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{S78}$$

and for ϕ as

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2C \sin^2(\theta) \cos(2\phi) \left(\frac{n_{45}}{A + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}-1} + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi))} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{n_{\text{tot}}}{4A + \frac{1}{\beta_0-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{135}-1} + 4B \sin^2(\theta)} \right) \\
& + 2C \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\phi) \left(\frac{n_{90}}{A + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}-1} + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \cos(2\phi))} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{n_{\text{tot}}}{4A + \frac{1}{\beta_0-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{135}-1} + 4B \sin^2(\theta)} \right) \\
& + 2C \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\phi) \left(\frac{n_{\text{tot}}}{4A + \frac{1}{\beta_0-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{135}-1} + 4B \sin^2(\theta)} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{n_0}{A + \frac{1}{\beta_0-1} + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \cos(2\phi))} \right) \\
& + 2C \sin^2(\theta) \cos(2\phi) \left(\frac{n_{\text{tot}}}{4A + \frac{1}{\beta_0-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{45}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{90}-1} + \frac{1}{\beta_{135}-1} + 4B \sin^2(\theta)} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \frac{n_{135}}{-A + \frac{1}{1-\beta_{135}} + \sin^2(\theta)(C \sin(2\phi) - B)} \right) = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{S79}$$

both of which may be numerically solved to give θ and ϕ . For the case without background, these reduce to

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{A + B \sin^2(\theta)} AC \sin(2\theta) \left(\cos(2\phi) \left(\frac{n_0}{A + (B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta)} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. - \frac{2n_{90}}{2A + B - B \cos(2\theta) - 2C \cos(2\phi) \sin^2(\theta)} \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 2 \sin(2\phi) \left(\frac{n_{45}}{2A + B - B \cos(2\theta) + 2C \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\phi)} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + \frac{n_{135}}{-2A - B + B \cos(2\theta) + 2C \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\phi)} \right) \right) = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{S80}$$

and for ϕ as

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2C \sin^2(\theta) \left(\sin(2\phi) \left(-\frac{n_0}{A + (B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta)} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + \frac{n_{90}}{A + (B - C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta)} \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \cos(2\phi) \left(\frac{n_{45}}{A + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi))} - \frac{n_{135}}{A + \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi))} \right) \right) = 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{S81}$$

For the case of 3 detectors (here, assumed 0, 45 and 90°) the MLEs are, for the case with background

$$\begin{aligned}
& (B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin(2\theta) \left(\frac{n_0}{A + (B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_0}} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{n_0 + n_{45} + n_{90}}{3A + \sin^2(\theta)(3B + C \sin(2\phi)) + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_0} + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{45}} + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{90}}} \right) \\
& + \sin(2\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) \left(\frac{n_{45}}{A + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{45}}} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{n_0 + n_{45} + n_{90}}{3A + \sin^2(\theta)(3B + C \sin(2\phi)) + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_0} + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{45}} + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{90}}} \right) \\
& + (B - C \cos(2\phi)) \sin(2\theta) \left(\frac{n_{90}}{A + (B - C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{90}}} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{n_0 + n_{45} + n_{90}}{3A + \sin^2(\theta)(3B + C \sin(2\phi)) + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_0} + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{45}} + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{90}}} \right) = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{S82}$$

for θ and

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2C \cos(2\phi) \sin^2(\theta) \left(\frac{n_{45}}{A + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{45}}} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{n_0 + n_{45} + n_{90}}{3A + \sin^2(\theta)(3B + C \sin(2\phi)) + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_0} + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{45}} + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{90}}} \right) \\
& + 2C \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\phi) \left(\frac{n_{90}}{A + (B - C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{90}}} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{n_0 + n_{45} + n_{90}}{3A + \sin^2(\theta)(3B + C \sin(2\phi)) + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_0} + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{45}} + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{90}}} \right) \\
& + 2C \sin^2(\theta) \sin(2\phi) \left(-\frac{n_0}{A + (B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta) + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_0}} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \frac{n_0 + n_{45} + n_{90}}{3A + \sin^2(\theta)(3B + C \sin(2\phi)) + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_0} + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{45}} + \frac{1}{-1+\beta_{90}}} \right) = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{S83}$$

for ϕ . In the case without background, these reduce to

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{3A + \sin^2(\theta)(3B + C \sin(2\phi))} AC \sin(2\theta) \left(\frac{(3 \cos(2\phi) - \sin(2\phi))n_0}{A + (B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta)} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \frac{2 \sin(2\phi)n_{45}}{A + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi))} - \frac{(3 \cos(2\phi) + \sin(2\phi))n_{90}}{A + (B - C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta)} \right) = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{S84}$$

for θ and

$$\begin{aligned}
& 2C \sin^2(\theta) \left(\left(-\frac{\sin(2\phi)}{A + (B + C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta)} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. - \frac{\cos(2\phi)}{3A + \sin^2(\theta)(3B + C \sin(2\phi))} \right) n_0 + \frac{\sin(2\phi)n_{90}}{A + (B - C \cos(2\phi)) \sin^2(\theta)} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \frac{\cos(2\phi) (2 (A + B \sin^2(\theta)) n_{45} - (A + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi))) n_{90})}{(A + \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi))) (3A + \sin^2(\theta)(3B + C \sin(2\phi)))} \right) = 0
\end{aligned} \tag{S85}$$

for ϕ .

S2 Measurement Uncertainty Limits as $n_{\text{tot}} \rightarrow \infty$

Here we show, for multiple β , the behavior of the measurement uncertainty in θ and ϕ as $n_{\text{tot}} \rightarrow \infty$. We would expect, intuitively, that our measurement uncertainty $\rightarrow 0$ as $n_{\text{tot}} \rightarrow \infty$. This intuition can be backed up by taking the limits of the $J_{\phi\phi}$ and $J_{\theta\theta}$ terms, in addition to a numerical approach. We will here show the limits of equations S62 and S60 as examples to show the limiting behavior. The limits of the scattering-based equations behave the same with respect to $n_{\text{tot}} \rightarrow \infty$, but due to the lengthy nature of the equations the derivation is somewhat involved and thus not useful to clarify the limiting behavior. To take the limits of equation S62, we first make the simplifications that $I_0^\beta = I_{45}^\beta = I_{90}^\beta = I_{135}^\beta = I^\beta$ and $\beta_0 = \beta_{45} = \beta_{90} = \beta_{135} = \beta$. We also make the substitution of $I^\beta = I/(1 - \beta^{-1})$ and $\beta = (I + I_{\text{bkg}})/I_{\text{bkg}}$.

$$\begin{aligned}
J_{\phi\phi,f} = & C^2 I^2 T \sin^4(\theta) (I(2A + B) - BI \cos(2\theta) + 2I_{\text{bkg}}) (I^2 (32A^2 + 32AB + 12B^2 - 9C^2) \\
& - 4I \cos(2\theta) (8B(AI + I_{\text{bkg}}) + 4B^2I - 3C^2I) + 32I_{\text{bkg}}I(2A + B) \\
& + I^2 ((4B^2 - 3C^2) \cos(4\theta) - 8C^2 \sin^4(\theta) \cos(8\phi)) \\
& + 32I_{\text{bkg}}^2) / \left(8 (AI + I \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi)) + I_{\text{bkg}}) (AI + I \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) \right. \\
& \left. + I_{\text{bkg}}) (AI + I \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \cos(2\phi)) + I_{\text{bkg}}) (AI + I \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \cos(2\phi)) + I_{\text{bkg}}) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S86}$$

To find the limits of this equation, we make use of L'Hôpital's rule, defining equation S86 as $f(I)/g(I)$ and taking derivatives to get $f''(I)$ and $g''(I)$. These are

$$\begin{aligned}
f''(I) = 4C^2T \sin^4(\theta) & \left(I \cos(2\theta) (-15I^2 (2B (16A^2 + 16AB + 5B^2) - C^2(8A + 7B))) \right. \\
& - 72I_{\text{bkg}}I (4B(2A + B) - C^2) - 144BI_{\text{bkg}}^2 + 5BC^2I^2 (8 \sin^4(\theta) \cos(8\phi) + 3 \cos(4\theta)) \\
& + 6I_{\text{bkg}}I^2 (96A^2 + 96AB + 28B^2 - 9C^2) + 5I^3(2A + B) (32A^2 + 32AB + 12B^2 - 9C^2) \\
& + I^2 ((4B^2 - 3C^2) \cos(4\theta)(5I(2A + B) + 6I_{\text{bkg}}) \\
& \quad \left. - 8C^2 \sin^4(\theta) \cos(8\phi)(5I(2A + B) + 6I_{\text{bkg}}) - 10B^3I \cos(6\theta)) \right. \\
& \left. + 144I_{\text{bkg}}^2I(2A + B) + 4BI^2 \cos^2(2\theta) (5I (4B(2A + B) - 3C^2) + 24BI_{\text{bkg}}) + 32I_{\text{bkg}}^3 \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S87}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
g''(I) = 4 & \left(4 (6B^2 - C^2) \sin^4(\theta) (6A^2I^2 + 6AI_{\text{bkg}}I + I_{\text{bkg}}^2) + 24A^2(AI + I_{\text{bkg}})^2 \right. \\
& + 24BI (2B^2 - C^2) \sin^6(\theta)(2AI + I_{\text{bkg}}) + 48AB \sin^2(\theta)(AI + I_{\text{bkg}})(2AI + I_{\text{bkg}}) \\
& \left. + 3I^2 \sin^8(\theta) (-8B^2C^2 + 8B^4 - C^4 \cos(8\phi) + C^4) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S88}$$

to simplify these somewhat unwieldy equations, we make the assumption that $I_{\text{bkg}} = 0$, a valid assumption as such a value is in both of these equations it is always multiplied by I . This simplifies our equations to

$$\begin{aligned}
f''(I) = 4C^2T \sin^4(\theta) & \left(I \cos(2\theta) (5BC^2I^2 (8 \sin^4(\theta) \cos(8\phi) + 3 \cos(4\theta)) \right. \\
& \quad \left. - 15I^2 (2B (16A^2 + 16AB + 5B^2) - C^2(8A + 7B))) \right. \\
& + 5I^3(2A + B) (32A^2 + 32AB + 12B^2 - 9C^2) \\
& + I^2 (5I(2A + B) (4B^2 - 3C^2) \cos(4\theta) - 40C^2I(2A + B) \sin^4(\theta) \cos(8\phi) \\
& \quad \left. - 10B^3I \cos(6\theta)) + 20BI^3 \cos^2(2\theta) (4B(2A + B) - 3C^2) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S89}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
g''(I) = 4 & \left(24A^2I^2 (6B^2 - C^2) \sin^4(\theta) + 96A^3BI^2 \sin^2(\theta) + 24A^4I^2 \right. \\
& \left. + 48ABI^2 (2B^2 - C^2) \sin^6(\theta) + 3I^2 \sin^8(\theta) (-8B^2C^2 + 8B^4 - C^4 \cos(8\phi) + C^4) \right).
\end{aligned} \tag{S90}$$

Collecting terms, this gives us

$$\begin{aligned}
f''(I) = & 4C^2 I^3 T \sin^4(\theta) \left(-15 \cos(2\theta) (2B (16A^2 + 16AB + 5B^2) - C^2(8A + 7B)) \right. \\
& + 5(2A + B) (32A^2 + 32AB + 12B^2 - 9C^2) + 5(2A + B) (4B^2 - 3C^2) \cos(4\theta) \\
& - 40C^2(2A + B) \sin^4(\theta) \cos(8\phi) + 20B \cos^2(2\theta) (4B(2A + B) - 3C^2) \\
& \left. - 10B^3 \cos(6\theta) + 5BC^2 \cos(2\theta) (8 \sin^4(\theta) \cos(8\phi) + 3 \cos(4\theta)) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S91}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
g''(I) = & 4I^2 \left(24A^2 (6B^2 - C^2) \sin^4(\theta) + 96A^3 B \sin^2(\theta) + 24A^4 \right. \\
& \left. + 48AB (2B^2 - C^2) \sin^6(\theta) + 3 \sin^8(\theta) (-8B^2 C^2 + 8B^4 - C^4 \cos(8\phi) + C^4) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S92}$$

Thus, where our prefactor of $\sin^4 \theta \neq 0$, such an equation clearly tends to infinity as we have

$$\lim_{I \rightarrow \infty} J_{\phi\phi, f} \propto \frac{I^3}{I^2} \equiv I$$

and also

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} J_{\phi\phi, f} \propto T$$

Thus we expect, at everywhere save $\theta = 0$, for the measurement uncertainty to tend to 0 as $n_{\text{tot}} \rightarrow \infty$ or $T \rightarrow \infty$, as intuited. At $\theta = 0$ we have $\sin^4 \theta = 0$ and thus $0 \times \infty$. This thus means that at infinity this function at $\theta = 0^\circ$ is undefined (as $0 \times \infty$ is undefined). Thus for the purposes of plotting our measurement uncertainty, and observing if it does collapse as a function of $n_{\text{tot}}^{-1/2}$, we take an average omitting the θ of 0° . It is clear from the analytical expressions that it must collapse as a function of $n_{\text{tot}}^{-1/2}$ as the Fisher information is linear in I , which is linear in n_{tot} thus the Cramér-Rao lower bound must have a $n_{\text{tot}}^{-1/2}$ dependence.

For determining the limit of equation S60, we first make the same simplifications as above— $I_0^\beta = I_{45}^\beta = I_{90}^\beta = I_{135}^\beta = I^\beta$ and $\beta_0 = \beta_{45} = \beta_{90} = \beta_{135} = \beta$. We again make the substitution of $I^\beta = I/(1 - \beta^{-1})$ and $\beta = (I + I_{\text{bkg}})/I_{\text{bkg}}$. This leads to

$$\begin{aligned}
J_{\theta\theta,f} = & 2TI^2 \sin^2(2\theta) \left(C^2 \cos^2(2\phi) (AI + BI \sin^2(\theta) + I_{\text{bkg}}) ((AI + I_{\text{bkg}})^2 - 2B^2 I^2 \sin^4(\theta)) \right. \\
& + \frac{1}{4} (I^2 \sin^4(\theta)(AI + I_{\text{bkg}}) (4B^2 C^2 \cos(4\phi) - 4B^2 C^2 + 24B^4 + C^4 \cos(8\phi) - C^4) \\
& \quad + 2BI \sin^2(\theta)(AI + I_{\text{bkg}})^2 (12B^2 - C^2 \cos(4\phi) + C^2) \\
& \quad \quad + 4(AI + I_{\text{bkg}})^3 (2B^2 + C^2 \sin^2(2\phi)) \\
& \quad \quad \quad \left. + 2BI^3 \sin^6(\theta) (-4B^2 C^2 \sin^2(2\phi) + 4B^4 + C^4 \sin^2(4\phi)) \right) / \\
& \left(AI + I \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \sin(2\phi)) + I_{\text{bkg}} (AI + I \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \sin(2\phi)) + I_{\text{bkg}}) (AI \right. \\
& \quad \left. + I \sin^2(\theta)(B - C \cos(2\phi)) + I_{\text{bkg}}) (AI + I \sin^2(\theta)(B + C \cos(2\phi)) + I_{\text{bkg}}) \right). \tag{S93}
\end{aligned}$$

To find the limits of this equation, we make use of L'Hôpital's rule, defining equation S93 as $f(I)/g(I)$ and taking derivatives to get $f''(I)$ and $g''(I)$. These are

$$\begin{aligned}
f''(I) = & 2T \sin^2(2\theta) \left(BI \sin^2(\theta) (10A^2 I^2 + 12AI_{\text{bkg}} I + 3I_{\text{bkg}}^2) (12B^2 - C^2 \cos(4\phi) + C^2) \right. \\
& + 2(AI + I_{\text{bkg}}) (10A^2 I^2 + 8AI_{\text{bkg}} I + I_{\text{bkg}}^2) (2B^2 + C^2 \sin^2(2\phi)) \\
& + 2C^2 \cos^2(2\phi) (BI \sin^2(\theta) (10A^2 I^2 - 4BI \sin^2(\theta) (5AI + 5BI \sin^2(\theta) + 3I_{\text{bkg}}) \\
& \quad + 12AI_{\text{bkg}} I + 3I_{\text{bkg}}^2) + (AI + I_{\text{bkg}}) (10A^2 I^2 + 8AI_{\text{bkg}} I + I_{\text{bkg}}^2)) \\
& + I^2 \sin^4(\theta) (5AI + 3I_{\text{bkg}}) (4B^2 C^2 \cos(4\phi) - 4B^2 C^2 + 24B^4 + C^4 \cos(8\phi) - C^4) \\
& \left. + 10BI^3 \sin^6(\theta) (-4B^2 C^2 \sin^2(2\phi) + 4B^4 + C^4 \sin^2(4\phi)) \right) \tag{S94}
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
g''(I) = & 2 (6B^2 - C^2) \sin^4(\theta) (6A^2 I^2 + 6AI_{\text{bkg}} I + I_{\text{bkg}}^2) + 12A^2 (AI + I_{\text{bkg}})^2 \\
& + 12BI (2B^2 - C^2) \sin^6(\theta) (2AI + I_{\text{bkg}}) + 24AB \sin^2(\theta) (AI + I_{\text{bkg}}) (2AI + I_{\text{bkg}}) \\
& + \frac{3}{2} I^2 \sin^8(\theta) (-8B^2 C^2 + 8B^4 - C^4 \cos(8\phi) + C^4) \tag{S95}
\end{aligned}$$

to simplify these somewhat unwieldy expressions, we again make the assumption that $I_{\text{bkg}} = 0$. This simplifies our equations to

$$\begin{aligned}
f''(I) = 2T \sin^2(2\theta) & \left(10A^2BI^3 \sin^2(\theta) (12B^2 - C^2 \cos(4\phi) + C^2) + 20A^3I^3 (2B^2 + C^2 \sin^2(2\phi)) \right. \\
& + 2C^2 \cos^2(2\phi) (BI \sin^2(\theta) (10A^2I^2 - 4BI \sin^2(\theta) (5AI + 5BI \sin^2(\theta)))) + 10A^3I^3 \\
& + 5AI^3 \sin^4(\theta) (4B^2C^2 \cos(4\phi) - 4B^2C^2 + 24B^4 + C^4 \cos(8\phi) - C^4) \\
& \left. + 10BI^3 \sin^6(\theta) (-4B^2C^2 \sin^2(2\phi) + 4B^4 + C^4 \sin^2(4\phi)) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S96}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
g''(I) = 12A^2I^2 (6B^2 - C^2) \sin^4(\theta) + 48A^3BI^2 \sin^2(\theta) + 12A^4I^2 \\
+ 24ABI^2 (2B^2 - C^2) \sin^6(\theta) + \frac{3}{2}I^2 \sin^8(\theta) (-8B^2C^2 + 8B^4 - C^4 \cos(8\phi) + C^4).
\end{aligned} \tag{S97}$$

Collecting terms, this gives us

$$\begin{aligned}
f''(I) = 2TI^3 \sin^2(2\theta) & \left(10A^2B \sin^2(\theta) (12B^2 - C^2 \cos(4\phi) + C^2) + 20A^3 (2B^2 + C^2 \sin^2(2\phi)) \right. \\
& + 20A^2BC^2 \sin^2(\theta) \cos^2(2\phi) + 20A^3C^2 \cos^2(2\phi) - 40AB^2C^2 \sin^4(\theta) \cos^2(2\phi) \\
& + 5A \sin^4(\theta) (4B^2C^2 \cos(4\phi) - 4B^2C^2 + 24B^4 + C^4 \cos(8\phi) - C^4) \\
& \left. + 10B \sin^6(\theta) (-4B^2C^2 \sin^2(2\phi) + 4B^4 + C^4 \sin^2(4\phi)) - 40B^3C^2 \sin^6(\theta) \cos^2(2\phi) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S98}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
g''(I) = I^2 & \left(12A^2 (6B^2 - C^2) \sin^4(\theta) + 48A^3B \sin^2(\theta) + 12A^4 + 24AB (2B^2 - C^2) \sin^6(\theta) \right. \\
& \left. + \frac{3}{2} \sin^8(\theta) (-8B^2C^2 + 8B^4 - C^4 \cos(8\phi) + C^4) \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{S99}$$

Thus, where our prefactor term $\sin^2(2\theta) \neq 0$, such an equation clearly tends to infinity as we have

$$\lim_{I \rightarrow \infty} J_{\theta, f} \propto \frac{I^3}{I^2} \equiv I$$

and also

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} J_{\theta, f} \propto T$$

and hence the measurement uncertainty must converge to 0 at $n_{\text{tot}} \rightarrow \infty$ or $T \rightarrow \infty$, as we intuited. Such a limit changes when our prefactor $\sin^2(2\theta) = 0$, (i.e., $\theta = 0, 90^\circ$), as the numerator then tends to $0 \times \infty$. This thus means that at infinity this function at $\theta = 0, 90^\circ$ is undefined (as $0 \times \infty$ is undefined). Thus for the purposes of plotting our measurement uncertainty, and observing if it does collapse as a function of $n_{\text{tot}}^{-1/2}$, we take an average omitting the θ of 0 and 90° . We note that in effect what this tells us is that in principle it is not possible to precisely identify if the θ value is at either of these two poles as the intensity at the detectors will be identical to that at another θ value.

Below we give the prefactors for computing the measurement uncertainty for fluorescence (for the case of Rh6G fluorophore collecting fluorescence from the peak wavelength of 547 nm) and scattering (for the case of 92 nm $\times$ 40 nm Au rod illuminated at 671 nm). The equation to compute the measurement uncertainty is

$$\sigma_{ij} = p_c(\beta)n_{\text{tot}} \quad (\text{S100})$$

with the β -dependence given by the equation

$$p_c(\beta) = (A * \sum_{i=1}^{i=2} a_i \exp(-\beta/\tau_i)) + C \quad (\text{S101})$$

with the fit parameters for scattering and fluorescence given in the tables S1–S4.

Table S1: Fit of β -dependence of p_c for ϕ scattering case.

A	a_1	τ_1	a_2	τ_2	C
52.7769	0.397956	18.2651	149.492	1.81343	57.0206

Table S2: Fit of β -dependence of p_c for θ scattering case.

A	a_1	τ_1	a_2	τ_2	C
6.16636	52.9123	27.8962	1529.55	2.35847	411.083

A fit of the model for fluorescence data is shown in Fig S1.

Table S3: Fit of β -dependence of p_c for ϕ fluorescence case.

A	a_1	τ_1	a_2	τ_2	C
65.9319	0.313989	18.4332	146.063	1.82171	55.474

Table S4: Fit of β -dependence of p_c for θ fluorescence case.

A	a_1	τ_1	a_2	τ_2	C
2.14528	583.478	2.65004	292.403	35.6205	288.645

Figure S1: a) How the uncertainty in θ (upper panel) and ϕ (lower panel) changes as $n_{\text{tot}} \rightarrow \infty$. $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$ and fluorescence spectra used was that of Rh6G. Filter width set as 1 nm at 547 nm. b) Fits to $\beta = \infty$ data using a model of $p_c \cdot n_{\text{tot}}^{-1/2}$, where p_c is a proportionality constant.

S3 Number of detectors and alignment

Here we show the effect of utilizing 3 vs. 4 detectors (with the same number photons per detector in each case). As is clear, 4 detectors always outperforms 3. In addition, we show the effect of changing the weight of intensity at detector k for the fluorescence case (Fig. S5).

Figure S2: Change in $\overline{(\sin \theta) \sigma_{\phi \phi}}$ (averaged across θ) as a function of ϕ with respect to changing the weight of intensity at detector k at each different detector. $\text{NA}_{\text{cond}}=1.3$, $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$ and the scatterer was simulated as a 92×40 nm Au rod, illuminated by a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at 671 nm.

Figure S3: Change in $\overline{(\sin \theta) \sigma_{\theta \theta}}$ (averaged across θ) as a function of ϕ with respect to changing the weight of intensity at detector k at each different detector. $\text{NA}_{\text{cond}}=1.3$, $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$ and the scatterer was simulated as a 92×40 nm Au rod, illuminated by a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at 671 nm.

Figure S4: Difference in measurement uncertainty for 4 detectors and 3 detectors (computed as $\sigma_{ii,k=3} - \sigma_{ii,k=4}$) for a) ϕ and b) θ . 4 detectors outperform 3 at all values. $\text{NA}_{\text{cond}}=1.3$, $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$ and the scatterer was simulated as a 92×40 nm Au rod, illuminated by a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at 671 nm.

Figure S5: Effect of changing the weight of intensity at detector k on measurement uncertainty in a) θ and b) ϕ . $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$ and fluorescence spectra used was that of Rh6G. Filter width set as 1 nm at 547 nm. $n_{\text{tot}} = 1000$, $\beta = 100$. Inset shows a zoom of the 0° detector measurement uncertainty change around the 0.5–1.5 weight region.

S4 Dependence of Intensity on θ

Here we show plots of how the overall scattered/emitted intensity changes with respect to the θ of the particle.

Figure S6: Dependence of scattered/emitted light on θ calculated using equations 7 and 13, such that a freely rotating particle would average an intensity of 1. Only NA_{obj} was used in the calculation of the fluorescent particle.

S5 Changing NA, Fluorescence Case

Here we show the effect of changing the NA of the objective on the measurement uncertainty in the case of measuring orientation of a fluorophore.

Figure S7: Effect changing NA_{obj} on measurement uncertainty for a fluorophore. Uncertainty change is in degrees relative to lowest σ_{ij} value. Fluorophore simulated as Rh6G, collection wavelength of 547 nm. Filter width set as 1 nm. $n_{\text{tot}} = 1000$, $\beta = \infty$.

S6 The effect of detection wavelength range in fluorescence

Here we show the effect of changing the collected wavelength on fluorescence measurement uncertainty (Fig. S8) and the effect of changing the range of collected wavelengths on fluorescence measurement uncertainty (Fig. S9).

Figure S8: Effect of fluorescence collection λ on measurement uncertainty for a) ϕ and b) θ for Rh6G fluorescence. The λ has minimal effect on the measurement uncertainty. $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$ was used for the calculation of the fluorescent particle. Here $n_{\text{tot}}=100$, $\beta=100$. Filter width=1 nm.

Figure S9: Filter width of fluorescence collection filter on measurement uncertainty for a) ϕ and b) θ for Rh6G fluorescence. The filter width has minimal effect on the measurement uncertainty. $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$ was used for the calculation of the fluorescent particle. Filter centred at 547 nm.

S7 The effect of material on measurement uncertainty

Here we show the effect of changing material of the nanorod on the measurement uncertainty, showing the spectral separation of the transverse and longitudinal plasmons for three different rod materials (Fig. S10) the effect of the rod dimensions on the measurement uncertainty (Fig. S11), the breakdown of the model of Yu *et al.* (Fig. S12) and the effect of ξ for a prolate ellipsoid on the measurement uncertainty (Fig. S13). We also show the effect of changing the luminophore on the measurement uncertainty (Fig. S14).

Figure S10: Spectra of rods of different materials, specifically an Au rod of $92 \times 40 \text{ nm}^2$, an Ag rod of $92 \times 30.5 \text{ nm}^2$ and a Cu rod of $92 \times 40.25 \text{ nm}^2$. Transverse and longitudinal contributions to the total extinction spectra are shown.

Figure S11: Effect of particle length L , width W and aspect ratio, $R=L/W$, on a) $\sigma_{\phi\phi}$ and b) $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ for different materials. Here $n_{\text{tot}}=1000$, $\beta=100$.

Figure S12: A demonstration of the breakdown of the model of Yu *et al.*³ at low aspect ratio, R . Here, the model calculates a negative extinction in some regions for the transverse plasmon resonance, an unphysical phenomenon.

Figure S13: Effect of ξ on a) $\sigma_{\phi\phi}$ and b) $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ for a prolate ellipsoid of different materials. Here $n_{\text{tot}}=1000$, $\beta=100$.

Figure S14: The effect of luminophore on measurement uncertainty for θ (top) and ϕ (bottom) as a function of intensity. $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$ and luminescence spectra used was that of Rh6G, Cy3 or a $6 \times 26 \text{ nm}^2$ Quantum Rod. Filter width set as 1 nm. Collection wavelengths are 547 nm for Rh6G, 566 nm for Cy3, and 611 nm for the QR. Also shown is the measurement uncertainty of an Au rod of $92 \text{ nm} \times 40 \text{ nm}$, $\text{NA}_{\text{cond}}=1.3$, $\text{NA}_{\text{obj}}=0.7$. Illumination source set as a lamp of 1 nm FWHM at 671 nm.

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